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D7.3 Population Health Data – policy and practice recommendations

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

ALPHA	Analysing Longitudinal Population-based HIV/AIDS data on Africa
APHRC	African Population Health Research Centre
ATHENA	Automated Terminology Harmonisation, Extraction and Normalisation for Analytics
CDIF	Cross Domain Interoperability Framework
CDM	Common Data Model
CODATA	Committee on Data of the International Science Council
CSV	Comma Separated Values
DDI	Data Documentation Initiative
DDI-CDI	DDI Cross Domain Integration
DHS	Demographic and Health Surveys
EHDEN	European Health Data and Evidence Network
ETL	Extract, Transform, Load
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reuseable
FDA	Food and Drug Administration
FIP	FAIR Implementation Profile
FNIH	Foundation for the National Institutes of Health
HDSS	Health and Demographic Surveillance System
ICD	International Classification of Diseases
IDSR	Infectious Disease Surveillance and Response
IMI	Innovative Medicines Initiative

INDEPTH	International Network for the Demographic Evaluation of Populations and Their Health
INSPIRE	Implementation Network for Sharing Population Information from Research Entities
JSON-LD	JavaScript Object Notation for Linked Data
LOINC	Logical Observation Identifiers Names and Codes
LSHTM	London School of Hygiene & Tropical Medicine
MADIMAH	Multi-centre Analysis of the Dynamics In Migration And Health
OHDSI	Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics
OMOP	Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership
PEPFAR	President's Emergency Plan For AIDS Relief
RxNORM	Normalised Medical Prescription
SERPS	Search Engine Results Pages
SNOMED-CT	Systemised Nomenclature Of Medical Clinical Terms
SQL	Structured Query Language
TRE	Trusted Research Environment
UNICEF	United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund
USAID	United States Agency for International Development
WHO	World Health Organisation
XML	Extensible Markup Language

Executive summary

This is the third and final deliverable from WorldFAIR WP07 on Population Health. Its primary aim is to provide a broad set of practical recommendations for health data producers in low- and middle-income countries who are seeking to make their data FAIR. This includes recommendations for: data documentation methods for those new to the process; harmonisation of data structures through use of a Common Data Model; standards for the publication of rich machine-readable metadata; methods for developing study packages to conduct federated analyses within and across domains; and the publication of FAIR Implementation Profiles.

This document is a synthesis of the discovery and work described in the two previous WP07 deliverables. As a reflection of the environment in which WP07 works, the methods proposed are open-source, freely available and frequently used. Some of them, such as the OHDSI/OMOP Common Data Model and the schema.org metadata standard, have grown in popularity in high-income settings and are underpinned by active user networks and freely available teaching resources. Their promotion here supports the argument for a coherent global standardisation of FAIR data methods, and this consistency promotes capacity building of the required data skills in lower-income settings that are integral to the adoption and success of FAIR data aspirations world-wide.

As well as reinforcing compatibility within the health data domain, WP07 has also chosen standards and methodologies that are compatible with other domains that comprise the WorldFAIR project. This approach is expanded in detail within WorldFAIR's WP02 Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF) which recognises that true interoperability of data - the ability to combine them in a scientifically rigorous way within and across domains - can dramatically enhance their value.

The intersections between population health, climate change and humanitarian crises are already acknowledged and within WorldFAIR itself: WP07 has clear links with urban health (WP08), social surveys (WP06), and disaster risk reduction (WP12). Such commonality in FAIR approaches across domains lies at the heart of what WorldFAIR seeks to achieve.

These recommendations are written for all health data producers in lower- and middle-income countries, regardless of their stage on the FAIR journey. Some may have little or no experience of data documentation; others may be ready to adopt a Common Data Model or publish machine-readable metadata; whilst others may be ready to conduct federated analyses. This document suggests recommendations for all, and these recommendations are consistent with those that would be made in higher-income settings.

The closing part of this document explores the burgeoning field of FAIR metrics - tools for measuring the extent to which FAIR has been achieved. This document does not add to this body of work because it takes the view that aiming for the FAIR principles by a data producer is such an individual and iterative process that following these recommendations, rather than applying an externally-generated metric, is more likely to achieve the goal of making health data FAIR.

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1. Introduction and target audience

This is the third and final deliverable from WorldFAIR Work Package WP07 on Population Health. WP07 is based upon a collaboration between the London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine (LSHTM)¹ and the Committee on Data of the International Science Council (CODATA)². These two institutions are also members of a larger collaborative body, the INSPIRE Network (Implementation Network for Sharing Population Information from Research Entities)³. INSPIRE is led by the African Population Health Research Centre (APHRC) in Nairobi⁴ with key collaborators from Kenya, Tanzania, Malawi and South Africa. INSPIRE's central objective is to empower data producers in low-income settings by providing tools and services that promote data sharing and reproducibility³.

The first two deliverables from WP07 were essentially instructional in nature. Deliverable 7.1 ("Implementation Guidelines for Annotating Health Research Data and Harmonisation: The INSPIRE Approach") provided guidance on producing structured metadata that could achieve FAIR principles⁵. Deliverable 7.2 ("Population health resource library and training package") continued this theme with a set of seven videos that together provided an introduction to creating a complete data pipeline from primary data to analytical datasets with machine-readable metadata⁶. The current and final deliverable, D7.3, reviews and consolidates this previous work into an overarching set of recommendations that cover both policy and practice. As a result it is thematically broader than its predecessors, it does not focus on one specific case study, and it is less technical in its content.

The document has been written with three key audiences in mind.

- The first audience is the organisations that are generating primary health-related data in low- and middle-income settings, and who are seeking guidance on making these data as FAIR as they can. Some of these agencies will have very little experience of data documentation, whereas others will be at an advanced stage and need advice on which standards to adopt. This document is written to cater for both of these groups and all those that lie between them.
- The second audience consists of the bodies that are funding the data producers, and who want to see the results of their investments meet FAIR principles. To do so requires specific funding of dedicated personnel with modern data science skills, and of information system infrastructures that can meet the burgeoning demands of technological change.
- Finally, this document has also been written for policy makers who themselves seek to provide guidance on good practice in producing FAIR data in the field of population health.

This document helps demonstrate that there is no shortage of population health data being generated by low- and middle-income countries. The challenge is to process these data to meet the FAIR objectives so that their full value can be realised.

2. Core concepts – metadata and FAIR data

2.1. Metadata

The simplest definition of metadata is that they are "data about data". If 'data' are the words in a novel in a bookshop then their metadata are the information that would make that novel findable within the shop, usually through an electronic search - the title, author, publisher, year of publication, floor number, shelf number and so on. Metadata could also include information that is less about the ability to find the novel and more about the purchaser's desire to read it - the genre, or number of pages, or reviews. The more detailed the metadata about the novel, the more informed the decision to buy it - even though the metadata would not contain a word of the novel itself.

In population health research, a substantial proportion of the data collected are quantitative and stored in a spreadsheet-type format that are also called datasets, tables or frames. The columns (also called variables or fields) each refer to a specific characteristic that is being measured. The rows (also called records or observations) refer to an individual subject on which these measurements have been taken. At the intersection of columns and rows are the cells containing the actual data themselves, results of a single measurement on a single subject. Metadata, while not a direct part of this matrix structure, are essential to explain the data – without it the data themselves will have no meaning. Metadata explains the characteristics being measured, such as their names, definitions, ranges and codes. The greater the detail of the metadata (called "granularity") the more information is provided about the data themselves and the easier are the decisions about what to do with it.

2.2. Working at scale and making data FAIR

Even the smallest research groups generating population health data need to produce the associated detailed metadata. But developments in information technology have created the opportunity to work with data at a scale never previously imagined. Data producers can now make their data available to a global research community of millions. As well as doing this for the advancement of knowledge and progress, many research groups are now required to make their data 'open' as a condition of funding.

How, in an environment as vast, random and uncontrollable as the Internet, can data be reliably found? Once found can they be readily accessed, and in a manner that does not critically compromise the privacy of the individuals who have contributed their health information? Can the value of the data be amplified through combination with other data from an entirely different research environment? And can these data be readily reused by other researchers in innovative ways? These characteristics denote the principles of data that are FAIR - **F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable and **R**eusable. In their simplest form, the FAIR principles are now well known⁷ and at their heart is a recognition that data are a valuable intellectual commodity and that the ability to

use, combine and reuse them should be maximised. In making data FAIR the metadata are indivisible from the data that they describe, as shown in the summary of FAIR principles in Table 1 below⁸.

FAIR principle	Reference	Description
Findable	F1	(Meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier
	F2	Data are described with rich metadata (defined by R1 below)
	F3	Metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data they describe
	F4	(Meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource
Accessible	A1	(Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standard communications protocol
	A1.1	The protocol is open, free, and universally implementable
	A1.2	The protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary
	A2	Metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available
Interoperable	I1	(Meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation
	I2	(Meta) data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles
	I3	(Meta) data include qualified references to other (meta)data
Reusable	R1	(Meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes
	R1.1	(Meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage licence
	R1.2	(Meta)data are associated with detailed provenance
	R1.3	(Meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards

Table 1: The FAIR principles

As the concept of FAIR matures, so too do the guidance and recommendations that help ensure the consistent technical and programmatic approach that FAIR relies upon. Technical ‘standards’ ultimately depend upon everyone doing the same thing, and the FAIR guiding principles have been described as scaffolding upon which members of research communities can develop their standards as consistent and coherent rules of engagement⁹.

The technical underpinning of producing FAIR data is not restricted to humans providing computers with data and metadata that other humans find and use. A central tenet of FAIR is that data and metadata should be both machine-readable and machine-actionable. In other words, data and metadata need to be produced in such a way that they conform to conventions that allow Internet search engines to identify them, reveal them and ideally cause them to interact with other relevant data, in a manner that requires as little human intervention as possible. This approach, and some recommended technical standards that can achieve it, are explained in the WorldFAIR Cross Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF)¹⁰. A number of the standards recommended in this document are based upon recommendations that the CDIF has made.

3. Data sources for WP07 Population Health and challenges in making these data FAIR

INSPIRE – and consequently WP07 – has predominantly focused upon health data generated in Eastern and Southern Africa. In terms of infrastructure and resources these can be regarded as similar to other low-income settings where the desire to make health data FAIR is gaining momentum. The absence of mature health systems means that a substantial proportion of data are collected outside of governmental settings. Organisations such as Demographic and Health Surveys (DHS), operated by USAID, and the Health and Demographic Surveillance Programmes were devised to help address a dearth of population health data that hampered the implementation of public health interventions. These differences in health system structures also mean that, when trying to produce FAIR data, low-income settings can find themselves in an unfamiliar environment of implementation standards and tools, most of which have been developed in higher-income settings. Below are some of the key population health data sources that have contributed to the work of INSPIRE, and some of the challenges that they pose.

3.1. Health and Demographic Surveillance Systems (HDSS)

A Health and Demographic Surveillance System (HDSS) describes a defined geographical location in which the entire population within that location are monitored for – at a minimum – births and deaths within the location, and migration in and out of it. Whilst the population is bound geographically, it is a temporally open cohort and regularly updates key characteristics as much as research requirements and resources allow. An HDSS population can also provide a comprehensive sampling frame for cross-sectional surveys that may focus on specific health conditions and

research questions. In some cases, the establishment of an HDSS has included the creation of a medical clinic within its perimeter that has enabled the collection of linked cohort and clinic data via the sharing of unique person identifiers¹¹.

HDSS were established in response to a lack of accurate population data in many African countries¹². A tenet of their establishment was that the detailed study of cultural, socio-economic and demographic characteristics of a population were essential to improving healthcare. The first HDSS was established in 1956 in Zambia and at the time of writing at least 35 exist throughout sub-Saharan Africa, with populations ranging from 20,000 to 250,000 individuals.

One of the defining characteristics of HDSS, as opposed to cross-sectional surveys such as those conducted by the DHS Programme, is that they are genuinely longitudinal. Each individual is traced from one year to the next, meaning that incidence rates – using periods of residence within the HDSS site as the denominator – can be produced.

3.2. National Ministry of Health Data

Ministries of Health will collect health data from the hospitals, clinics and other medical services that they run. These are usually a record of facility attendances and treatment administration and do not include any population or longitudinal components. The nature of the data will also be dependent upon the infrastructure at the health facilities – many rural clinics may not have electricity or any computing capability and so patient records are written into large ledger books, with summaries of attendances, diagnoses and treatment administration being provided to Health Ministries as hand-produced aggregate tables.

3.3. Non-governmental and academic organisations and research projects

This describes a wide range of health-related provision and consequent health data collection in low-income settings. International bodies such as WHO and UNICEF have extensive programmes in these settings, particularly in the fields of maternal and child health, prevention of childhood disease, nutrition and HIV/AIDS. Global programmes funded by overseas AID programmes, such as USAID¹³ and the US President's Emergency Plan for AIDS Relief (PEPFAR)¹⁴ can also have a strong presence and may fund work that is conducted in governmental or independently-run clinics. Not-for-profit organisations such as Medecins Sans Frontiers conduct large-scale vaccination programmes alongside their work in humanitarian relief¹⁵. Academic institutions will conduct short-term research programmes with all of the bodies above, with an emphasis upon detailed measurement and data collection.

Health care in low-income settings can therefore be characterised by a large number of contributors using a variety of bespoke but uncoordinated data systems. This isn't to say that approaches to data harmonisation haven't already been made. Groups such as INDEPTH (International Network for the Demographic Evaluation of Populations and their Health)¹⁶, ALPHA (Analysing Longitudinal

Population-based HIV/AIDS Data on Africa)¹⁷ and MADIMAH (Multi-centre Analysis of the Dynamics In Migration And Health)¹⁸ all focused upon the pooling and harmonisation of data from a range of sources, and of these INDEPTH achieved the greatest scale with 22 HDSS contributing standardised micro-datasets to the project's repository¹⁹. Nevertheless these approaches were not able to fully explore interoperability, either with other aspects of the health domain or with domains unrelated to health.

3.4. Challenges faced by low-income settings in making health data FAIR

As alluded to above, primary collection of population data in low-income settings often faces the following challenges:

- Extremely diverse IT infrastructures, data collection platforms and data collection formats
- Immature or outdated IT infrastructure
- Limited exposure and access to FAIR related technologies
- High volumes of individual-level health data, often considered to be highly sensitive due to the medical conditions recorded
- Poorly documented standard operating procedures and data provenance
- An absence of rich metadata
- Little development of standardised vocabularies to describe data values
- Vulnerable financial stability, particularly for repeated rounds of HDSS data collection.

In the following narrative, we suggest recommendations to start tackling some of these challenges.

4. Best practice and policy recommendations

4.1. Recommendations for data producers new to data documentation

4.1.1. Summary of recommendations

The WP07 Working Group recommends that data producers who have little or no experience of developing metadata for their primary data collection first gain experience using the tools and guidance produced by the Data Documentation Initiative. This will give exposure to producing metadata, working with standard vocabularies and publishing metadata in a form which is machine-readable. The version of DDI to use (DDI Codebook or DDI Lifecycle) will depend upon the study design being documented.

The Working Group also recommends that funding agencies recognise the need to pay for staff who are specifically trained in data documentation methods and who can implement a data documentation plan that will form the underpinning to meeting FAIR data objectives.

4.1.2. Introduction

The specific circumstances relating to low-income settings described in Section 3 can often mean that all of the available time, energy and money may be focused upon collecting and using data at the local level where they are felt to be most needed. Funding and personnel may simply have been insufficient to embark upon a programme of data documentation and yet without this, the aim of producing FAIR data can never be achieved. For those data producers who have not conducted data documentation before, the established methodologies created and promoted by the Data Documentation Initiative can be a valuable starting point and go some way towards meeting FAIR data objectives.

4.1.3. The Data Documentation Initiative

The Data Documentation Initiative (DDI) is an international standard for describing the primary data produced by observational methods in the social, economic and life sciences²⁰. It is maintained by the DDI Alliance which is hosted by the University of Michigan²¹. It is used by a wide variety of organisations, perhaps most notably in this case the International Household Survey Network which comprises statistical agencies in over 200 low and middle-income countries²².

DDI can document each stage of the research data lifecycle, from conceptualisation through to collection, processing, distribution and archiving. It provides a structure for describing research data; a standard that supports data sharing, understanding and reuse; and a mechanism that can facilitate the creation of consistent and machine-actionable documentation²³. DDI enables the creation and use of metadata and expresses this in XML markup that promotes machine-readability.

4.1.4. Versions of DDI

DDI is currently available in two versions, with a third soon to be released for production. These are free software products that can be redistributed and modified under their public licences and come with no warranty.

4.1.4.1. DDI Codebook (DDI – C, current version 2.5)

DDI Codebook was designed for the creation of metadata for simple cross-sectional survey data that does not include longitudinal data. It provides a structure with which to describe the basic content of files, variables, source material and study-level information. It is available at <https://ddialliance.org/Specification/DDI-Codebook/2.5/>.

4.1.4.2. DDI Lifecycle (DDI – L, current version 3.3)

Expressly designed for longitudinal data, DDI Lifecycle is designed to document and manage data across the entire data life cycle. This includes the description of multiple waves of longitudinal/repeated data collection, the description of comparison and harmonisation, the description of data collection and survey instruments, and support for centralised metadata management. It is available at <https://ddialliance.org/Specification/DDI-Lifecycle/3.3/>.

4.1.4.3. DDI Cross Domain Integration (DDI – CDI)

DDI-CDI is a model-based specification that can be more easily managed, extended and expressed in different representations. It is currently under public review and is not yet released for production. The WorldFAIR Cross Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF) is likely to recommend the use of DDI-CDI as the standard for the description of multi-dimensional data that is used across different data-collecting communities and domains, and therefore will be the most appropriate for describing data interoperability within FAIR.

4.1.4.4. DDI controlled vocabularies

A controlled vocabulary restricts the options available for describing the different components of data. This applies to the data structure, such as tables and variables, and the data values themselves, such as the way in which medical diagnoses or treatments are described. A controlled vocabulary can be a simple list or a much more complex hierarchical structure. Ideally, controlled vocabularies should be comprehensive, mutually exclusive (categories overlapping each other generate uncertainty) and clearly defined. It is always advisable to use controlled vocabularies where possible, to achieve consistency across different data sources and therefore to increase the potential for data interoperability. More information on the definitions and use of controlled vocabularies is given in section 4.2. The DDI controlled vocabularies are available at <https://ddialliance.org/controlled-vocabularies>.

4.1.5. DDI resources and tools

4.1.5.1. DDI Training materials

The DDI Alliance offers free-to-use training materials to aid with the use of its products. These training materials are online at <https://ddialliance.org/learn/training-materials>.

4.1.5.2. Nesstar Publisher (current version 4.0.10)

Nesstar is a free data documentation application produced by the Norwegian Social Science Data Services (NSD). It provides a user interface through which a data structure can be imported and associated metadata then generated using a suite of tools. The resulting data documentation complies with the DDI Initiative and with Dublin Core metadata standards. It also enables the use of controlled vocabularies and the metadata output can be generated in XML for reading into web pages and Internet searching. It is a desktop application that requires the Windows operating system. More information is available at: <https://www.ihsn.org/software/ddi-metadata-editor>.

4.2. The OHDSI Common Data Model

4.2.1. Summary of recommendations

The WorldFAIR WP07 group recommends that data producers who have some experience in data documentation:

- make the organisational decision to adopt the OHDSI Common Data Model (CDM) as a key step to making population health data FAIR
- review source data to determine which datasets and variables are to be included in a CDM
- use the open-source tools provided by OHDSI (White Rabbit, Rabbit-in-a-Hat and Osagi) to analyse the source data, document the restructuring of source data into the CDM, and incorporate codes from standardised vocabularies
- develop programmes and/or applications that will conduct the Extract, Transform and Load process (ETL) whereby source data are transformed into the CDM structure
- appoint designated staff with skills in each of the areas outlined above.

4.2.2. Introduction

A Common Data Model (CDM) has been broadly defined as "any standardised data model which allows for data and information exchange between different applications and data sources"²⁴. For the purposes of population health this often refers to standardising data storage within relational databases so that data could, in principle, be readily exchanged between them without needing to restructure the data storage. Doing this enables larger datasets to be generated across multiple data providers that are more generalisable and provide greater power for statistical analyses. They also enable the sharing of methodology, computer applications and code, thereby increasing efficiency; and they contribute substantially to greater collaboration and communication in research²⁵.

4.2.3. Using the OHDSI/OMOP Common Data Model

The Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership (OMOP) was formed in 2007 as a partnership between the US Foundation for the National Institutes of Health (FNIH), the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) and several pharmaceutical companies. Its initial aim was to study adverse drug reactions and improve the safety of medical products, and a component of this work was to develop methodology and tools for characterising, transforming and analysing data from different sources²⁶. From this came the shareable, standardised database structure that is the OMOP Common Data Model (OMOP CDM). OMOP was originally a five-year programme but in 2014 the Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics (OHDSI) Initiative was founded²⁷ and this has taken forward the development of the OMOP CDM. OHDSI is an open-science community with approximately 2,000 members in 74 countries.

Part of the reason for our recommendation here is that OHDSI/OMOP comprises a robust network of contributors that offers regular training and development activities. Due to the nature of its origins OHDSI/OMOP has largely reflected the needs of data collaboration in higher-income countries, and in particular the insurance-based model of the United States. Nevertheless OHDSI is

keen to broaden its applicability (its Africa Chapter is evidence of this) and adaptations to its methods are increasingly accommodating the requirements of lower-income settings.

An indispensable resource in developing an OMOP Common Data Model is the Book of OHDSI²⁸ which gives a thorough explanation of the requirements. At its heart lies the simple premise illustrated in Figure 1, of heterogeneous source data being transformed into the Common Data Model to facilitate standardised analyses.

Figure 1: Concept of the OHDSI/OMOP Common Data Model
(Source: <https://www.ohdsi.org/data-standardization>)

4.2.4. Structure of the OHDSI Common Data Model

The OHDSI Common Data Model (CDM) describes a relational database structure that is “person-centric” – that is to say, the central table is one that holds one unique record per person. This table holds a small number of key demographic variables for each individual – data on sex (called gender in the CDM), date of birth, race and ethnicity. Each individual is identified by a unique ID number which connects that individual to their data in a series of related tables. The current stable version of the CDM, for which the OHDSI-provided software tools function, is version 5.4, which is illustrated below in Figure 2.

Figure 2: OHDSI/OMOP Common Data Model version 5.4
(Source: <https://ohdsi.github.io/CommonDataModel/>)

Below is a summary of the role of each table in the standardised clinical data section of the CDM. Further details of each table, including information on datatypes and primary/foreign keys, can be found at:

https://ohdsi.github.io/CommonDataModel/cdm54.html#Current_Support_for_CDM_v54.

Table Name	Description
Person	Records that uniquely identify each person or patient in the model, with some demographic information on sex, race and ethnicity.
Observation_period	Records for each Person that define a specific span of time; clinical events that happened to the Person during each span of time are recorded in the events table.
Death	The clinical event for how and when a Person dies.
Visit_occurrence	Records of the events in which Persons engage with the healthcare system for a duration of time. Includes details of where this engagement took place, who the medical personnel were and whether the visit included becoming an inpatient.

Visit detail	An optional table that records details of medical care that took place within the timespan of the visit_occurrence table. This can include movement between different parts of a healthcare facility.
Condition_occurrence	Records the presence of a disease or medical condition stated as a diagnosis, a sign, or a symptom, which is either observed by a medical staff or reported by the patient.
Drug_exposure	This contains one record for each drug exposure. Drugs are defined as a biochemical substance and includes prescribed and non-prescribed medicines, vaccines and molecular therapies. The definition does not include radiological devices.
Procedure_occurrence	Any activity requested or provided by a healthcare provider that has a diagnostic or therapeutic purpose for the patient.
Device_exposure	Data about exposure to a physical object or instrument used for diagnostic or treatment purposes that does not rely on chemical action. This includes pacemakers, stents, artificial joints, bandages, crutches, defibrillators.
Measurement	Records the measurements obtained through the systematic examination or testing of a Person or Person's sample. This includes laboratory tests, vital signs and quantitative findings from pathology reports. They are stored as attribute/value pairs, whereby the attribute is the concept representing what is being measured, and the value is the numerical result. differ from Observations in that they require a standardised test or some other activity to generate a quantitative or qualitative result. If there is no result, it is assumed that the lab test was conducted but the result was not captured.
Observation	This table largely captures information that cannot be captured in other tables described, such as social and lifestyle information, medical history and family history.
Note	Unstructured information that was recorded by a provider about a Person in free text.
Note_NLP	This encodes all output of Natural Language Processing (NLP) on clinical notes. Each row represents a single extracted term from a note.
Episode	This aggregates data from records in visit_occurrence, drug_exposure, procedure_occurrence and device_exposure into a representation of disease phases, outcomes and treatments.

Episode_event	This connects qualifying clinical events from visit_occurrence, drug_exposure, procedure_occurrence and device_exposure to the appropriate Episode entry.
Fact_relationship	This contains records about the relationships between data stored in any table of the CDM. Examples include: Person relationships (parent-child), care site relationships (hierarchical organisational structure of facilities within a health system), indication relationship (between drug exposures and associated conditions), usage relationships (of devices during the course of an associated procedure), or facts derived from one another (measurements derived from an associated specimen).

Table 2: Descriptions of standardised clinical data tables in the OMOP CDM.

4.2.5. Standardised vocabularies in OMOP

We first referred to standardised (also called controlled) vocabularies in section 4.1. These are essentially common naming and classification systems for medical terminology that are shared between different users.

Name	Abbreviation	Description
International Statistical Classification of Diseases and Related Health Problems	ICD	A globally-used medical classification, maintained by the WHO, used in epidemiology, health management and for a wide range of clinical purposes. The current version is ICD-11 which came into effect on 1st January 2022.
Systemised Nomenclature of Medical Clinical Terms	SNOMED-CT	Primarily encodes clinical data in a patient record.
Logical Observation Identifiers Names and Codes	LOINC	Used for identifying health measurements, observations and documents. Codes can be grouped into laboratory and clinical tests, measurements and observations.
Normalised Medical Prescription	RxNorm	Used to normalise names for clinical drugs, and links names to commonly used drug vocabularies.

Table 3: Some common controlled vocabularies used in electronic health records

The standardisation reduces ambiguity in medical terms, increases efficiency in recording information and reduces the likelihood of errors. A large number of different vocabularies have emerged to meet the needs of different organisations but, as such diversity can diminish the value of standardisation, some of these have coalesced into a smaller number of vocabularies that are more widely used. Some of the most common ones are listed in Table 3.

As well as the standardisation and mapping of terminologies for use in research, the OMOP standardised vocabularies act as a common repository for all the vocabularies used within the OHDSI community, and they are all standardised to the same format. Within the Common Data Model, the standardised vocabularies are a mandatory reference table and therefore must be used when restructuring source data into the CDM. Currently there are 111 vocabularies that are supported by OMOP, of which 78 have been adopted from external sources.

All clinical events in OMOP are expressed as concepts that are contained within the concept table of the CDM. This contains a unique identifier for each concept together with fields for other attributes of the vocabulary term. An example of this, taken from Chapter 5 of the Book of OHDSI, is shown in Figure 3.

CONCEPT_ID	313217	← Primary key
CONCEPT_NAME	Atrial fibrillation	← English description
DOMAIN_ID	Condition	← Domain
VOCABULARY_ID	SNOMED	← Vocabulary
CONCEPT_CLASS_ID	Clinical Finding	← Class in vocabulary
STANDARD_CONCEPT	S	← Standard, Source of Classification
CONCEPT_CODE	49436004	← Code in vocabulary
VALID_START_DATE	01-Jan-1970	← Valid during time interval
VALID_END_DATE	31-Dec-2099	
INVALID_REASON		

Figure 3: A vocabulary concept taken from the vocabulary CDM table
(Source: <https://ohdsi.github.io/TheBookOfOhdsi/StandardizedVocabularies.html>)

OHDSI has developed a Web application that enables the distribution and browsing of all the standardised vocabularies that can be used in an OMOP CDM. This application is ATHENA – The Automated Terminology Harmonisation, Extraction and Normalisation for Analytics. ATHENA has full search functionality, as well as the initial grouping of vocabularies into domains on the application home page.

Figure 4: The OHDSI ATHENA home page
(Source: <https://athena.ohdsi.org/search-terms/start>)

4.2.6. From source data to CDM – Extract, Transform and Load (ETL).

In this context, the ‘Extract, Transform and Load’ (ETL) process refers to identifying the source data that will populate the CDM, restructuring it into the CDM tables and loading it into these tables. As far as possible this process should be automated so that it can be easily repeated when the source data are updated.

A more detailed overview of this process is given in Chapter 6 of the Book of OHDSI. Key steps in the ETL process are:

- The source data are reviewed to determine which of the source tables and their variables will be included in the CDM.
- The selected source data are analysed using OHDSI’s ‘White Rabbit’ tool.
- The output from ‘White Rabbit’, in the form of a spreadsheet, is used in OHDSI’s ‘Rabbit in a Hat’ tool to assist in the restricting of data from the source tables/variables to the OMOP CDM equivalents. Mapping includes the introduction of standard concept IDs.
- The resulting description of the remapping is translated into ETL programmes that carry out the data restructuring and load the CDM tables and variables appropriately.

4.2.7. OHDSI tools for carrying out Extract, Transform and Load

4.2.7.1. OHDSI ‘White Rabbit’

White Rabbit is an open-source software application developed by OHDSI which conducts an analysis of a source dataset and publishes a summary of results into a spreadsheet²⁹. This

spreadsheet is then used as the data source for the subsequent data-mapping process that is carried out using “Rabbit-in-a-Hat” (see section 4.2.7.2).

A source dataset can be input into White Rabbit as a comma-separated (CSV) file or as a database table held in MySQL, SQL server, Oracle, PostgreSQL, Microsoft APS, Microsoft Access or Amazon RedShift database applications. From the input source White Rabbit generates a summary of the dataset characteristics, fields and values that are held within each field. The resulting report does not display any personally identifiable information.

4.2.7.2. OHDSI ‘Rabbit-in-a-Hat’

The spreadsheet created by the OHDSI White Rabbit tool is used to create a document that describes the mapping of tables and variables from the source data to those in the Common Data Model. This mapping is facilitated by another OHDSI open-source software application – ‘Rabbit-in-a-Hat’.

This application creates a visual interface that shows the structure of the source data alongside the structure of corresponding CDM tables. The illustration below (Figure 5), taken from Chapter 6 of the Book of OHDSI³⁰ shows an example of data held in a “person” table in a source dataset, the corresponding structure of the Person table in the CDM and the conversion of variables from one structure to the other. The grey arrows are obtained by dragging and dropping a coloured box representing a variable from the source data column (here in orange) into the corresponding variable in the CDM (here in purple). Whilst simple, this illustration demonstrates some important principles:

- A single variable in the source data can populate multiple variables in the CDM. An example of this is the birthdate variable in the source data which can be seen to populate four variables in the CDM.
- Data mapping extensively makes use of standardised concept IDs as part of data standardisation, and the individuals responsible for conducting this mapping will benefit from advanced knowledge of the codes that denote, for example, the different categories of sex, race and ethnicity. The CDM also permits the recording of the source values for those variables which are also described by concepts. Therefore, for example, the variable for gender in the source data is mapped into two variables in the CDM – the gender concept ID which is standardised and the gender source value which is retained for reference and is specific to the source data.
- Rabbit-in-a-Hat is a documentation tool – it describes the required ETL but it does not then carry any of it out. Therefore detailed textual instructions need to be provided alongside the visual mapping exercise, and an example of this for the CMD person table is shown in Table 4.

Figure 5: Example of mapping a source data table to a CDM Person table

(Source: <https://ohdsi.github.io/TheBookOfOhdsi/ExtractTransformLoad.html#step-3-implement-the-etl>)

GENDER_CONCEPT_ID	gender	When gender = 'M' then set GENDER_CONCEPT_ID to 8507, when gender = 'F' then set to 8532. Drop any rows with missing/unknown gender. These two concepts were chosen as they are the only two standard concepts in the gender domain. The choice to drop patients with unknown genders tends to be site-based, though it is recommended they are removed as people without a gender are excluded from analyses.
YEAR_OF_BIRTH	birthdate	Take year from birthdate
MONTH_OF_BIRTH	birthdate	Take month from birthdate
DAY_OF_BIRTH	birthdate	Take day from birthdate
BIRTH_DATETIME	birthdate	With midnight as time 00:00:00. Here, the source did not supply a time of birth so the choice was made to set it at midnight.
RACE_CONCEPT_ID	race	When race = 'WHITE' then set as 8527, when race = 'BLACK' then set as 8516, when race = 'ASIAN' then set as 8515, otherwise set as 0. These concepts were chosen because they are the standard concepts belonging to the race domain that most closely align with the race categories in the source.
ETHNICITY_CONCEPT_ID	race ethnicity	When race = 'HISPANIC', or when ethnicity in ('CENTRAL_AMERICAN', 'DOMINICAN', 'MEXICAN', 'PUERTO_RICAN', 'SOUTH_AMERICAN') then set as 38003563, otherwise set as 0. This is a good example of how multiple source columns can contribute to one CDM column. In the CDM ethnicity is represented as either Hispanic or not Hispanic so values from both the source column race and source column ethnicity will determine this value.

Table 4: ETL logic required to convert the source table to the CDM PERSON table. (Source: <https://ohdsi.github.io/TheBookOfOhdsi/ExtractTransformLoad.html#step-3-implement-the-etl>)

4.2.7.3. OHDSI 'USAGI'

Usagi (Japanese for rabbit) is another tool developed by OHDSI to assist in the mapping of codes from source data into the concepts used by the standardised vocabularies in the Common Data Model. Codes from the source data can be loaded into the Usagi interface in a .csv or .xlsx format.

Relevant search parameters are chosen and Usagi then conducts a search of the best matching concepts that already exist within OMOP standardised vocabularies. An indicator of the strength of the match is also given and the option is then available to modify matches manually. An example of the Usagi interface is given in Figure 6 below.

The screenshot displays the Usagi interface with three main sections highlighted by red boxes and arrows:

- Overview table:** A table listing source data and its mapping to standard concepts. The table has columns for Status, Source code, Source term, Frequency, Dutch term, Match score, Concept ID, Domain, Concept class, Vocabulary, Concept code, Standard con., Parents, Children, and Comment.
- Selected mapping:** A detailed view of a specific mapping for source code 5774012 (General disease) to concept ID 435569 (Disorder of jaw).
- Search facility:** A search interface with a query field, filters (e.g., Filter by user selected concepts, Filter by standard concepts), and a results table showing alternative mappings.

Figure 6: An example of a Usagi results table. (Source: as Figure 5)

In this example above, the overview table shows how records from the source data have been automatically mapped onto concept names in the OMOP standardised vocabularies. The section for selected mapping shows a larger view of the mapping that has been proposed by Usagi. The search pane suggests relevant alternatives, if the proposed mapping could be improved upon.

4.3. Producing structured machine-readable metadata

4.3.1. Summary of recommendations

The WorldFAIR WP07 working group recommends that data producers:-

- produce “machine-readable” structured metadata that are published on the web
- use the schema.org standard to produce machine-readable metadata
- uses JSON-LD as the coding application to define schema.org data structures.

4.3.2. What are structured machine-readable metadata?

Internet search engines are now searching, indexing and ranking a vast quantity of heterogeneous electronic data, and returning the results in search engine results pages (SERPs). It has been estimated that Google alone has reviewed over 130 trillion web pages. A data producer that is seeking to make its data FAIR will want the metadata to be returned in the results of these search engines, and would want as much detail of the metadata to be revealed as possible. This requires the production of structured metadata – metadata written with standardised formats and vocabularies that is more readily identified, indexed and returned by search engines (i.e. is machine-readable). It also means that more detail of the metadata is revealed in the search, meaning that more informed decisions can be made about its re-use.

4.3.3. What is schema.org?

Schema.org is a collaboration established in 2011 between some of the major internet search engines companies (including Google, Bing and Yahoo) which has a principle aim of developing and expanding standardised coding structures for metadata (called schemas) that can be added to the programming of webpages, in order to improve how search engines understand and display the content. Schema.org improves the “understanding” of search engines of metadata content, thereby increasing the likelihood that the metadata will be identified and returned in search results. It can also provide context to otherwise ambiguous web pages by exposing the structured information to the reader.

4.3.4. What is JSON-LD?

Schema.org structures can be written using a variety of programming applications. One of the most popular, and the one recommended by Google for structured data, is JSON-LD (JavaScript Object Notation for Linked Data). This has been developed specifically to express information using structured data vocabularies such as schema.org. JSON-LD embeds information into web pages so that it is hidden from human users but visible to computer search engines.

JSON-LD helps fulfil FAIR objectives in the following ways:-

Findable: it allows data publishers to embed rich metadata into their web pages, which can be easily discovered by search engines and other machine-based operations.

Accessible: it is a lightweight and human-readable format, making it easy for both humans and machines to access and process.

Interoperable: it uses standard vocabularies and ontologies which makes it easy to integrate data from different sources.

Reusable: it provides clear and concise descriptions of data, which makes it easy for others to reuse data in new and innovative ways. This includes areas such as licensing, usage rights and community standards.

4.3.5. Schema.org and the OHDSI Common Data Model

In order to express the tables and fields in the OHDSI Common Data Model as structured metadata, there needs to be a consistent approach to using the types and properties that are available in schema.org. One approach to this was demonstrated at an OHDSI community initiative – the COVID-19 ‘study-a-thon’ – that was organised collaboratively between the Innovative Medicines Initiative (IMI) and the EHDEN Project. This is now the basis of a “recipe” in the FAIR “cookbook”³¹ – “FAIRification of observational studies and databases: the EHDEN and OHDSI use case” (‘use case’ is a term frequently used in this field to mean a case study). In Section 5.1, it states that the main objective of this work was to “make observational health databases and observational studies more Findable (notably the FAIR principles F2 and F4) and interoperable (principles I1 and I2) by creating a metadata model and a human and machine readable website for dissemination of these resources”.

The first step in this process is described as identification of the digital resources that are used. This includes the OMOP CDM itself and the standardised vocabularies. Next, rich structured metadata were generated using the schema.org environment. The following schema.org types were the most relevant in doing this:

- **Dataset:** represents a data file or database resulting from the study
- **MedicalObservationalStudy:** main type that represents the medical study itself
- **MedicalObservationalStudyDesign:** provides details about the design of the study
- **MedicalStudyStatus:** provides the status of the study (although this is based on clinical trials, and observational studies will not use all statuses)
- **MedicalCondition:** used to link the study to the specific medical condition(s) it covers
- **Drug:** used to link the study to any pharmaceutical products it covers
- **Organisation:** represents an organisation, such as a university
- **Person:** represents a person and is mainly used to indicate the authors of/researchers involved in the study.

The schema.org type ‘MedicalObservationalStudy’ was the core type from which the others were connected. This is shown diagrammatically below in Figure 7, in which a literal (coloured in yellow) refers to a string or enumerated value taken from a list, and a ‘class’ (coloured in orange) is a more complex type that can contain sub-fields.

Figure 7: EHDEN COVID Study-a-thon Metadata Model (CC BY)

Source: <https://eqonw.github.io/cookbook-dev/content/recipes/applied-examples/ehden-ohdsi.html>

4.4. Developing study packages

4.4.1. Summary of recommendations

The WP07 working group recommends that data producers with experience of the OHDSI/OMOP CDM, schema.org and JSON-LD use these tools to develop study packages that incorporate study designs and cohort definitions. These can be used by other organisations with similar data structures and objectives to conduct federated analyses and generate aggregate results that can be shared.

4.4.2. What is meant by a ‘study package’?

Our recommendations so far have focused upon the restructuring of source data into a Common Data Model and the creation of rich, structured metadata that describes the components of the model in a way that they can be readily discovered by internet search engines and returned in their results pages. An additional component to this is the capacity of the methods described to enable the conduct of research studies rather than just the description of them.

This requires the development of study packages – catalogues of metadata that can be shared between data producers and which give full instructions on how a specific research project should be carried out.

One increasingly important reason for working in this way is the diminishing ability for data producers to share their source data directly with one another. Expanding threats to data security mean that health data producers must be scrupulous about protecting their patient data – which are almost always sensitive in nature – from unwanted disclosure. This means that research studies are increasingly “federated” in their execution – the data remain within the secure environment of the data producers and the metadata required for the design and execution of a study are shared between those who have a desire to contribute. They use these metadata to run a study and produce aggregated results from which all individual identification has been removed. These aggregated results can then be pooled across different data producers, and can themselves be given a rich metadata description.

A significant part of the OHDSI environment is the tools that can be used to run such studies and generate aggregated results. This includes ATLAS, an open-source tool for conducting analyses of observational data that have been restructured into the CDM format. These analyses rely upon the definition of cohorts – defined groups of people based on an exposure to a specific drug or diagnosis. Those individuals who meet medical criteria specified in ATLAS are referred to as the target cohort. Those who experience a subsequent and previously-defined outcome are referred to as the outcome cohort. Formulating these cohorts within the CDM environment means that the definitions can in theory be shared with a range of data producers who are also using their data within that environment.

An example of such a study package, including cohort definitions, is shown in Figure 8 below, which has been developed by INSPIRE and is expressed entirely using the schema.org standard. Some components of this will already be familiar from Figure 7, notably the schema.org type ‘MedicalObservationalStudy’ (and the properties that stem from that such as the study title, identifier, and status), and the class of medical observational study design.

The ETL process of restructuring source data into the CDM is also shown in the boxes circled in red. For these analyses, the source data was derived from the WHO Infectious Disease Surveillance and Response (IDSR) programme. Restructuring these source data into the CDM tables is represented by the ETL SQL class, which encapsulates the programming requirements that have, in this case, been carried out using Structured Query Language (SQL). All of this work is called directly by the MedicalObservationalStudy type using the UpdateAction type. This schema includes two types of analysis, a predictive analysis and an incident rate analysis. Each of these contain the target and outcome cohorts as described above (circled in blue).

Figure 8: The INSPIRE data model for schema.org. Source: <https://zenodo.org/records/7887385>

A key element of FAIR metadata is that it is both machine-readable and actionable by machines. By taking the approach outlined above, it is feasible that a rich metadata description could be automatically assessed alongside the contents of a CDM to determine whether those data could be analysed in the manner that the metadata suggests. This approach is also common outside of the health data domain. The combination of schema.org with JSON-LD is one that has been recommended by the WorldFAIR Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF).

5. Metrics considerations for standards-setting bodies

5.1. Quantitative FAIR metrics

5.1.1. Recommendation

With regard to the settings in which it has been developing FAIR methodologies, the WPO7 Working Group is not proposing the development of an additional metric tool with which data producers can assess whether their practices are FAIR. Instead we recommend that data producers in low- and middle-income countries aim to adopt the recommendations presented here, as appropriate to their stage of data documentation, and assess FAIR attainment by drafting a FAIR Implementation Profile.

In many respects, the FAIR principles can be regarded as aspirational – they do not suggest strict methodologies in their approach and their requirements are deliberately permissive, in order to remain achievable by the large variety of data settings in which they hope to be applied. Nevertheless, data producers - as they embark upon a journey towards FAIR data - will want some kind of indication of the moment at which they have arrived. This brings with it a desire for FAIR to be measurable, and out of this has come a range of quantitative tools which aim to do that.

The aim of these tools is to produce a measurement of FAIR achievement that is meaningful to an individual data-producer in its own right, and which can also enable comparison across data producers operating in the same field or domain. It can be argued that this can help to enhance collaboration between institutions, if the potentials released by data being FAIR at one institution can be readily recognised and evaluated by others.

FAIR measurement, or FAIR metrics, take a number of different forms, and evaluations of FAIR measurement tools themselves are also becoming more commonplace. One component of this work is the FAIR Metrics Group which aims to define ways of measuring FAIRness itself³². In this pursuit it has identified nine characteristics of a FAIR measurement tool:

- Metrics should address the multi-dimensionality of the FAIR principles, and encompass all types of digital objects;
- Universal metrics may be complemented by additional resource-specific metrics that reflect the expectations of particular communities;

- The metrics themselves, and any results stemming from their application, must be FAIR;
- Open standards around the metrics should foster a vibrant ecosystem of FAIRness assessment tools;
- Various approaches to FAIR assessment should be enabled (e.g. self-assessment, task forces, crowdsourcing, automated), however, the ability to scale FAIRness assessments to billions if not trillions of diverse digital objects is critical;
- FAIRness assessments should be kept up to date, and all assessments should be versioned, have a timestamp, and be publicly accessible;
- FAIRness assessments presented as a simple visualisation will be a powerful modality to inform users and guide the work of producers of digital resources;
- The assessment process, and the resulting FAIRness assessment, should be designed and disseminated in a manner that positively incentivises the providers of digital resources; i.e., they should view the process as being fair and unbiased, and moreover, should benefit from these assessments and use them as an opportunity to identify areas of improvement ;
- Governance over the metrics, and the mechanisms for assessing them, will be required to enable their careful evolution and address valid disagreements.

Developing such a measurement tool is therefore a complex process if it is to capture and reflect all of the scenarios to which it could be applied. As a result methodologies have been based upon different interpretations of what may be required, and heterogenous FAIR assessment tools have been the result.

To address this, the Research Data Alliance set up a working group of over 200 members – The FAIR Data Maturity Model³³ – to develop criteria to enable comparison across assessment approaches. The Working Group identified 12 different FAIR evaluation tools and assessed each one in relation to the four cornerstone principles of FAIR³⁴. It concluded with a further set of indicators that would enable these methodologies and tools to be compared between themselves. This demonstrates the complexity of a field that aims to apply firm quantitative measures to principles that were deliberately devised to allow for flexibility.

This field of FAIR metrics and FAIR metric evaluation is one that will continue to expand and become more refined. Further standardisation of metrics will continue to emerge and ultimately these tools could play a valuable role in providing a quick ‘snapshot’ of the attainment of FAIR by an individual agency, and some comparison of this attainment between agencies.

However, being mindful of the settings that it seeks to support, WorldFAIR WP07 is not suggesting that data producers in low- and middle settings make use of the metrics currently available, and it is not advocating producing a further metric to add to those that exist. The reason for this is that, as this document demonstrates, attaining FAIR principles is a detailed, iterative, and highly individual process for a data producer, and many of the agencies for whom this document is written will be in

the early stages of this process. This will take time and resources to implement but, by using a combination of the recommendations suggested here and the template of the FAIR Implementation Profile (FIP), data producers will be able to assess for themselves whether and when the principles of FAIR have been achieved. This is likely to provide a more realistic and recognisable measure of achievement than applying an external metric.

5.2. FAIR Implementation Profiles

5.2.1. Recommendation

WP07 recommends the use of FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs). A FIP is essentially a summary of the choices that a specific organisation or community has made in order to implement each aspect of their FAIR principles. Organised as a set of questions, the FIP asks data producers to detail the practical steps that have been taken to achieve each FAIR principle. For each principle there is a corresponding FAIR Enabling Resource (FER) that makes possible the implementation of each principle.

For data producers, a FIP has three specific advantages.

- The first is that it provides a centralised and coherent documentation of each of the methods that have been adopted to achieve each FAIR principle.
- The second is that the FIP is a standardised approach to enabling FAIR, and FAIR Enabling Resource (FERs) can potentially be reused by other data-producing communities to meet similar objectives. This is efficient in terms of reducing duplication, but also increases the likelihood of convergence towards a smaller number of established FAIR-enabling conventions.
- The third is that the FIP can itself be expressed as a machine-actionable dataset.

In its simplest form, a FIP is a spreadsheet in which each FAIR principle has a corresponding FAIR Enabling Resource (FER). A modified example of this is given in Figure 9 and a spreadsheet version is available from <https://bit.ly/yourFIP>.

The machine-actionable version of a FIP can be developed by using the FIP Wizard <https://fip-wizard.ds-wizard.org/wizard/>. This provides an online questionnaire in which each of the FIP questions can be answered and where the FAIR Enabling Resources can be documented as “nano-publications”. These can then be re-used by other data-collecting communities which increases standardisation, conversion and efficiency.

FAIR principle	Question	FAIR enabling resource types	Your answers
F1	What globally unique, persistent, resolvable identifiers do you use for metadata records?	Identifier type	e.g. PURL, DOI
F1	What globally unique, persistent, resolvable identifiers do you use for datasets?	Identifier type	
F2	Which metadata schemas do you use for findability?	Metadata schema	
F3	What is the technology that links the persistent identifiers of your data to the metadata description?	Metadata-Data linking mechanism	
F4	In which search engines are your metadata records indexed?	Search engines	
F4	In which search engines are your datasets indexed?	Search engines	
A1.1	Which standardized communication protocol do you use for metadata records?	Communication protocol	
A1.1	Which standardized communication protocol do you use for datasets?	Communication protocol	
A1.2	Which authentication & authorisation technique do you use for metadata records?	Authentication & authorisation technique	
A1.2	Which authentication & authorisation technique do you use for datasets?	Authentication & authorisation technique	
A2	Which metadata longevity plan do you use?	Metadata longevity	
I1	Which knowledge representation languages (allowing machine interoperation) do you use for metadata records?	Knowledge representation language	
I1	Which knowledge representation languages (allowing machine interoperation) do you use for datasets?	Knowledge representation language	
I2	Which structured vocabularies do you use to annotate your metadata records?	Structured vocabularies	
I2	Which structured vocabularies do you use to encode your datasets?	Structured vocabularies	
I3	Which models, schema(s) do you use for your metadata records?	Metadata schema	
I3	Which models, schema(s) do you use for your datasets?	Data schema	
R1.1	Which usage license do you use for your metadata records?	Data usage license	
R1.1	Which usage license do you use for your datasets?	Data usage license	
R1.2	Which metadata schemas do you use for describing the provenance of your metadata records?	Provenance model	
R1.2	Which metadata schemas do you use for describing the provenance of your datasets?	Provenance model	

Figure 9: FIP mini questionnaire (Source: <https://bit.ly/yourFIP>)

6. Conclusions and next steps

The recommendations presented in this document aim to reflect the needs of the broad range of organisations in lower- and middle-income countries that are producing health-related data and who are seeking to make these data FAIR. They also aim to reflect current technological realities which set the boundaries in terms of required skills and potential costs. It is this technical environment, which we have no choice but to join, that is most subject to change. Information technology possesses a voracious appetite for growth and modification, and with each new iteration comes a commensurate expansion of potential risk. Behind our rows and columns of data lie individuals with medical information that they do not wish to be shared and for whom disclosure can carry substantial personal detriment.

Data producers who are taking these threats seriously are increasingly sealing their data within their own research environments to eliminate the risk of miscreant disclosure in the wider world. Researchers can send their analytical plans to be executed by the institutions who own the data, and as a result sensitive personal information may never be seen by the analysts. The creation of study packages described in Section 7 reflect steps towards this approach, but it is this area that is likely to undergo extensive change with the growth of Trusted Research Environments (TREs)³⁵, bastions of data safety with multiple levels of authenticated data access and the quarantine and verification of any outputs before release. TREs also provide highly-configured ‘workbenches’ of tools and services, single hubs of data storage and scalable computing power.

Creating such a TRE is beyond the capacity of most data producers in low- and middle-income countries, but the growth of international platforms such as INSPIRE can bring the resources and expertise closer to those organisations who may not be able to develop such platforms on their

own. This growth of such secure and standardised platforms will continue the trajectory that has been set by FAIR.

7. Summary of recommendations

Recommendation type: Technical (Metadata)
Recommendation theme: Data producers new to data documentation
Report section: 4.1
Stakeholders: Data producers, funding agencies
Recommendation:

The WP07 Working Group recommends that data producers who have little or no experience of developing metadata for their primary data collection gain experience first using the tools and guidance produced by the Data Documentation Initiative. This will give exposure to producing metadata, working with standard vocabularies and publishing metadata in a form which is machine-readable. The version of DDI to use (DDI Codebook or DDI Lifecycle) will depend upon the study design being documented. The Working Group also recommends that funding agencies recognise the need to pay for staff who are specifically trained in data documentation methods and who can implement a data documentation plan that will form the underpinning to meeting FAIR data objectives.

Recommendation type: Technical (Metadata)
Recommendation theme: The Common Data Model
Report section: 4.2
Stakeholders: Data producers, funding agencies
Recommendation:

The WP7 group recommends that data producers who have some experience in data documentation:

- make the organisational decision to adopt the OHDSI Common Data Model (CDM) as a key step to making population health data FAIR;
- review source data to determine which datasets and variables are to be included in a CDM;
- use the open-source tools provided by OHDSI (White Rabbit, Rabbit-in-a-Hat and Osagi) to analyse the source data, document the restructuring of source data into the CDM, and incorporate codes from standardised vocabularies;
- develop programmes and/or applications that will conduct the Extract, Transform and Load process (ETL) whereby source data are transformed into the CDM structure;
- appoint designated staff with skills in each of the areas outlined above.

Recommendation type: Technical (Metadata)
Recommendation theme: Producing machine-readable metadata
Report section: 4.3
Stakeholders: Data producers, funding agencies
Recommendation:

The WP7 working group recommends that data producers:

- produce “machine-readable” structured metadata that are published on the web;
- use the schema.org standard to produce machine-readable metadata;
- uses JSON-LD as the coding application to define schema.org data structures.

Recommendation type: Technical (Metadata)
Recommendation theme: Developing study packages
Report section: 4.4
Stakeholders: Data producers
Recommendation:

The WP07 working group recommends that data producers with experience of the OHDSI/OMO CDM, schema.org and JSON-LD use these tools to develop study packages that incorporate study designs and cohort definitions. These can be used by other organisations with similar data structures and objectives to conduct federated analyses and generate aggregate results that can be shared.

Recommendation type: Policy
Recommendation theme: Development of a new FAIR metric
Report section: 5.1
Stakeholders: Data producers
Recommendation:

With regard to the settings in which it has been developing FAIR methodologies, the WP07 Working Group is not proposing the development of an additional metric tool with which data producers can assess whether their practices are FAIR. Instead it is recommending that data producers in low- and middle-income countries aim to adopt the recommendations presented here, as appropriate to their stage of data documentation, and to assess FAIR attainment by drafting a FAIR Implementation Profile.

Recommendation type: Technical (metadata); technical (data); policy

Recommendation theme: FAIR Implementation Profiles

Report section: 5.2

Stakeholders: Data producers

Recommendation:

WP07 recommends the use of FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs). A FIP is essentially a summary of the choices that a specific organisation (sometimes termed a community) has made in order to implement each aspect of their FAIR principles. Organised as a set of questions, the FIP asks data producers to detail the practical steps that have been taken to achieve each FAIR principle. For each principle there is a corresponding FAIR Enabling Resource (FER) that makes possible the implementation of each principle.

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